

DFMAS Project: IoT and DT application for evolution of services with low level of digitalization

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DF-MAS. Digital Fleet Maintenance Services

EL CLÚSTER TECNOLÓGICO Y BIOTECNOLÓGICO DEL SUR DE EUROPA

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DF-MAS

Digital Fleet Maintenance Services

Application:

- ✓ Advanced Digitalization of a **Critical Service** (Business and Security) with **Initially Low Digitalization Level**.

Servitization Orientation:

- ✓ Driving **Business Transformation** through **Services**.
- ✓ **Decision-Making centres**.
- ✓ **Assets & Services (A&S)** representation.

DTT (Digital Twin Technologies) approach:

- ✓ Development of **Models**.
- ✓ Identification of **Technologies** to be used in the project.
- ✓ **Integration of Data Management and Models Management**.
- ✓ **Unique Digital Representations of Entities: Assets and Services (A&S)**.

Digitization must be oriented towards a

Servitization approach:

- For the development of railway rolling stock fleet maintenance services.
- Including the safety requirements of the railway sector.
- Identifying key entities (assets, processes, services),
- Manage the models that complement the digital definition of these entities.
- Identifying and managing decision-making centers/level where model insights are required

Servitization approach + Digital Twin Approach

Analyzed business case study

Business needs

- Controlling the state of assets: traceability of components, condition (expiration + wear).
- Control of the execution of Fitness For Services (FSS) inspections: when, what is done, and performance (ensuring that all tasks are performed correctly by accredited personnel and technical resources and collecting all legally required data).

Proposed solutions

- Digitalization of service processes for Preventive Maintenance, Corrective Maintenance, and FFS.
- Digitalize the status variables of these components (definition of variables, collection and recording of attributes, and storage).
- Facilitate data entry for condition variables, machine operation, and workshop operation.
- Increase control capacity through artificial intelligence.
- Increase workshop planning capacity through planning and optimization models.

MODEL-BASED DT

Model-Based Approach: DTTs enable the definition of entities (Assets & Services) through a portfolio of models that can be interconnected and integrated.

Maintenance Management Requirements: The maintenance management framework serves as methodological support for guiding the development of models.

Scalability and Complexity: Avoiding unnecessary complexity is crucial, closely tied to scalability. Scalability in the digitalization lifecycle permits the evolution of digital representation. The framework provides a pathway for integrating evolving models based on service requirements.

MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

Basic entity definition process

- Definition of the data model of each Entity.
 - Assets.
 - Workshop (facility and building).
 - Workshop resources (equipment and tools).
 - Human resources.
- Definition of the Fitness For Service data model.
- Definition of the planning data models.

Integration in BIM
+
Transfer to platform

BIM + Transfer to platform requirements

- Development of 3D-BIM models
- Development of information capture and transmission devices (IoT).

Model design requirements

- Dynamic history control on equipment that can locate different Functional Locations (FL).
 - Technical Structure (TS), Entities, and the use of Classes.
- Codification of the TS and Entities.
 - We are assigning values to variables (attributes) of the Entities (Instantiation).
 - Tracing component variations in each asset and associating them with the BIM models.
 - Attribute-based tracking of components subject to wear and tear to consider possible substitutions of components.
- Coding of Fitness For Service tasks. Assignment of attributes to the variables of each task.
- Relationship between Tasks and Entities. Attribute sharing.

Data model of the asset / resource workshop:

- Physical Asset (Tamping M.) / Press-spring
 - Technical Structure (T.U.) / Expiration
 - Component classes
 - Reference system (asset position)

TS	Asset	System	Item n ₁	Item n ₂	Item n ₃	Item n ₄
	Tamping M.	S- Rolling	Bogie	Axle	Wheel	
					Grease box	Bearing
			Towing	Axle	Wheel	
					Grease box	Bearing

Service data model: Corrective, Preventive, FFS

- Functional structure of the asset (Failure Mode)
- Process (tasks associated with a component at the FM level)
- Task classes (inheritable by other DTs)
- Relationships (components, workshop resources, spare parts, scheduling models)

SR: Rolling System	T A S K S					
EJ: Axle	Internal faces Distance	Visual crack checking	Ultrasonic crack checking			
RD: Wheel	Flange Height	Flange Thickness	Flange slope	Wheel diameter	Rwheel tread relief	Metal plans
CG: Grease box	Grease state					
RT: Bearing	Bearing verification	Post bearing verification				

Optimisation model:

- Input data model
- Model design and programming.
- Output data model

Failure mode attributes:

- Failure and preventive hours, t_i

Economic attributes:

- Corrective and Preventive Costs, R_2, R_3, R_{21}, R_{31}
- Income from the use of the asset, R_1

Determines the optimal preventive interval of a task to maintain a failure mode.

Decision-making support

Task planning

Size of the optimal preventive interval, of the failure mode,

τ_0

Models and technologies integration

IoT link with physical assets

Cloud platform integration

Decision-Making Interfaces

Future animation of workshop assets and resources

- Representation of activities in the digital twin.
- Capture of the positions and uses of workshop assets and resources.
- Detection of differences between what is actually detected and what is digitally executed.
 - Taking measures to avoid deviations.

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Project: **digest**

DIGITAL TWIN WEEK

ESReDA

European Safety, Reliability & Data Association

Deusto
Universidad de Deusto

Join us for an upcoming event on Digital Twins, featuring a doctoral training session and a seminar that serves as a unique academia-industry gathering. Delve into the world of Digital Twins with our training and explore their key application in Digital Maintenance.

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64th ESReDA Seminar

**digital
maintenance in
the digital
twin era.**

30th
31th
may

ENHAnCE

Featuring Engineering

**doctoral
workshop on
digital twin.**

29th
30th
31th
may

BUILDCHAIN

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EVENT LOCATION
Universidad de Deusto
Bilbao (Spain)

Deusto
Universidad de Deusto

PROGRAMME

	Day 1 29th May	Day 2 30th May	Day 3 31th May
Doctoral Workshop	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Workshop Sessions</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Workshop Sessions</i>• <i>Gala Dinner</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Workshop Sessions</i>
64th ESReDA Seminar	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>ESReDA BoD meeting</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Seminar Sessions</i>• <i>ESReDA GA meeting</i>• <i>Gala Dinner</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Seminar Sessions</i>

Doctoral Workshop Agenda

DAY 1. WEDNESDAY 29 May

Start	End	Agenda Item
8:30	9:00	Welcome to the participants and COFFEE
9:00	10:00	Introduction to Digital Twinning Prof. Herman Matthies (TU Braunschweig, Germany)
10:00	10:30	BREAK
10:30	11:45	Introduction to Inverse Problems and their Probabilistic Treatment 1 Prof. Herman Matthies (TU Braunschweig, Germany)
11:45	12:00	COFFEE BREAK
12:00	13:15	Introduction to Inverse Problems and their Probabilistic Treatment 2 Prof. Herman Matthies (TU Braunschweig, Germany)
13:15	14:30	COCKTAIL LUNCH
14:30	15:45	Predictive/Proxi modeling, explainability of models 1 Prof. Anna Kucerova (CTU Prague)
15:45	16:00	COFFEE BREAK
16:00	17:15	Predictive/Proxi modeling, explainability of models 2 Prof. Andras Benczur (SZTAKI, Hungary)

Doctoral Workshop Agenda

DAY 2. Thursday 30 May

<i>Start</i>	<i>End</i>	<i>Agenda Item</i>
8:30	9:30	Predictive/proxi modeling, explainability of models 3 Prof. Andras Benczur (SZTAKI, Hungary)
9:30	10:15	PLENARY TALK: Digital Twin aiding more effective Digital Maintenance Diego López de Ipiña_DEUSTOTECH
10:15	11:15	Proxi modeling for stochastic systems 1 Prof. Herman Matthies (TU Braunschweig, Germany)
11:15	11:30	COFFEE BREAK
11:30	13:00	Proxi modeling for stochastic systems 2 Dr. Noemi Friedman (SZTAKI, Hungary)
13:00	14:00	COCKTAIL LUNCH
14:00	14:45	PLENARY TALK: Digital transformation in maintenance and asset management. Guidelines for organizations. Prof. Adolfo Crespo_UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA
14:45	15:30	Bayesian model updating and filtering and computational techniques 1 Prof. Juan Chiachío (University of Granada, Spain)
15:30	15:45	COFFEE BREAK
15:45	17:00	Bayesian model updating and filtering and computational techniques 2 Prof. Juan Chiachío (University of Granada, Spain)

Doctoral Workshop Agenda

DAY 3. Friday 31 May

<i>Start</i>	<i>End</i>	<i>Agenda Item</i>
8:30	9:30	BIM technologies and digital twinning 1 Ing. Francisco Carmona (QuantIA S.L., Spain)
9:30	10:15	PLENARY TALK: Identifying the Future Skills Requirements of the Digital Maintenance era Felix Bayon_SIDENOR
10:15	11:15	BIM technologies and digital twinning 2 Ing. Francisco Carmona (QuantIA S.L., Spain) & Prof. Manuel Chiachío (University of Granada, Spain)
11:15	11:30	COFFEE BREAK
11:30	13:00	Educative examples of the whole framework, summary Dr. Noemi Friedman (SZTAKI, Hungary)
13:10	13:40	Wrapping Up: Key Takeaways and Roundtable Discussion
13:40	14:25	COCKTAIL LUNCH

64th ESReDA Seminar Agenda

DAY 1. WEDNESDAY 29 May

<i>Start</i>	<i>End</i>	<i>Agenda Item</i>
16:30	18:00	ESReDA Board of Director meeting

DAY 2. Thursday 30 May

<i>Start</i>	<i>End</i>	<i>Agenda Item</i>
9:00	9:30	Welcome to the participants and COFFEE
9:30	10:15	PLENARY TALK: Digital Twin aiding more effective Digital Maintenance Diego López de Ipiña_DEUSTOTECH
10:15	11:15	AI for the application of maitenance techniques
10:15	10:30	Artificial Intelligence as a driver for Prescriptive Maintenance: Limitations Joaquín Ordieres_UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID
10:30	10:45	AI-Powered Models: Catalysts for Digital Twin Advancements in Industry 4.0 Maria Megía_UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA
10:45	11:00	A Review of Hybrid Prognostics Applications for Power & Energy Systems Joxe I. Aizpurua_MONDRAGON UNIBERTSITATEA
11:15	11:45	COFFEE BREAK
11:45	13:00	IoT and DT
11:45	12:00	An innovative IoT device designed to enhance teaching performance through the application of digital twin technology Diego Casado_DEUSTOTECH
12:00	12:15	Edge-Based AI for Online Health Monitoring of Critical Water Desalination Pumps: Aingura IIoT Applications in the Digital Twin Era David Cruz_AINGURA

12:15	12:30	Self-powered instrumentation systems for IoT and Maintenance Jorge Marcos Acevedo_ UNIVERSIDAD DE VIGO
12:30	12:45	Recalibration of Digital Twins via Mobile Agents Sascha Peitzsch_ FRAUNHOFER SIRIOS
13:00	14:00	COCKTAIL LUNCH
14:00	14:45	PLENARY TALK: PLENARY TALK: Digital transformation in maintenance and asset management. Guidelines for organizations. Adolfo Crespo_ UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA
14:45	15:45	DT Modelling and Simulation techniques I
14:45	15:00	A Petri net-based Digital Twin development for managing wind turbine blade maintenance Wen Wu_ UNIVERSITY OF NOTTINGHAM
15:00	15:15	"Towards Precision in Railway Corrugation Estimation: Employing CNN-1D Networks and Fractal Dimensions" Massoud Haghbin_ UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA
15:15	15:30	Basic architecture for digital twin implementation for power electronics application José López_ CEN SOLUTIONS, Juan Gómez_ UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA
15:45	16:00	COFFEE BREAK
16:00	17:00	DT Modelling and Simulation techniques II
16:00	16:15	Simulation on reliability analysis of linear consecutive K-out-of-n systems for Weibull parameter estimation with incomplete failure data Daniel Gaspar_ TECNICO DE LISBOA
16:15	16:30	Smart factory maintenance: building a predictive model of pathogen transmission during the food fabrication process Sébastien Delmotte_ MAD-Enviroment
16:30	16:45	Digital Twin-Assisted Predictive Maintenance (DT-PdM) Framework for Complex Systems: Preliminary Research through a Pilot Study Huxiao Shi_ Politecnico di Torino
16:45	17:00	Bases for Ontology of Digital Twin of Maintenance Process. A Railway Application Mauricio Rodríguez_ UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA
17:00	18:30	45th ESReDA General Assembly
20:30	-	Gala Dinner

64th ESReDA Seminar

DAY 3. Friday 31 May

<i>Start</i>	<i>End</i>	<i>Agenda Item</i>
9:00	9:30	Welcome to the participants and COFFEE
9:30	10:15	PLENARY TALK: Identifying the Future Skills Requirements of the Digital Maintenance era Felix Bayon_SIDENOR
10:15	11:15	Lines of value for DT and DM development: human centered and servitization
10:15	10:30	Vulnerabilities in the human factor-digital technology relationship in the railway system Sever Paul_AGIFER
10:30	10:45	The consideration of the Human-Machine Interface in the Safety Management System of the process industry Romulado Marrazzo_VAL-RTEC
10:45	11:00	DFMAS Project: IoT and DT application for evolution of services with low level of digitalization Antonio Sánchez_UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA
11:15	11:45	COFFEE BREAK
11:45	12:15	PLENARY TALK Service: the red pill. How to make industrial service a reality Ibon Iribarren_TIMEPACK
12:15	13:10	Digitalization for sustainability and management
12:15	12:30	Digital Twin technology in Civil Engineering: research vision from the ENHANCE and BUILDCHAIN European projects Manuel Chiachío_UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA

12:15	12:30	<p>Sustainable maintenance and digital twin technology: a test case for evaluating integration potentialities</p> <p>Maria Grazia Gnoni_ UNIVERSITY OF SALENTO</p>
12:30	12:45	<p>Impact of digitization on physical asset management</p> <p>Javier Serra_ENAGAS</p>
13:10	13:40	<p>Wrapping Up: Key Takeaways and Roundtable Discussion</p>
13:40	14:55	<p>COCKTAIL LUNCH</p>
-	-	<p>Free visit to the Guggenheim Museum Bilbao <i>(Limited number of invitations. To attend, registration will be open during the seminar until all available invitations are filled.)</i></p>

Location

Turin Room at Faculty of Engineering (2nd floor), Deusto.
Universidad de Deusto.

There will be indicative arrows to reach the Turin room once reached the entry of the Faculty of Engineering

